

Module 2	Scientific Programming Environment (SPE)
Course coordinator	Ruggero Lot (RL)
Lecturers	Niccolò Tosato , Gianfranco Gallizia and RL
Tutors	Massimo Luin
Class duration	21 hours
Module description	Introduction to Linux operating system and fundamental concepts of containers and container orchestration. In the first part, students will learn the Linux basics, including the command-line interface, file system navigation, user and package management, and collaborative tools. Additionally, the course covers essential Linux utilities, scripting, and an introduction to system administration concepts.
Main topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to Unix-like operating systems - (kernel vs. userspace, processes/threads, file system semantics) - Shell scripting (bourne shell) - Configuring, compiling, linking software packages - principal commands, shell, tools, and scripting [1, 4] - packet manager (dnf, yum, zipper, pacman) [4] - Groups, Resource monitoring [TBD] - Editors (Vim, nano) and file managers (ranger or broot, vim) [1] - Command line environment [1, 4], org.freedesktop standard [3] - Access control (permission, groups, home) [4], selinux - Collaborative source code management: Git [1, 2] - File system [4] - Network configuration [5] - Integrated development environments - Visualization tools: - Debugging tools
Objectives	On successful completion of this module students should have their own software environment and tools prepared and configured for the rest of the activities of the master program. Students will learn the workflows of software development and collaborative work. These concepts are the basis on which efficient data application and workflow for data management will be developed.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [1] the missing semester, mit https://missing.csail.mit.edu/), - [2] pro git (https://git-scm.com/book/en/v2) - [3] freedesktop specs and thereafter (https://specifications.freedesktop.org/basedir-spec/basedir-spec-latest.html) - [4] Learning Modern Linux (978-1-098-10894-6) - [5] Computer Networking (978-0-13-285620-1)